

MANO, Manuscripts Online: A Collaborative Platform for Digital Manuscript Studies

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Introduction

In the Digital Humanities academic context, particularly within courses on digital manuscript studies, the focus is often on theoretical knowledge of XML, Text Encoding Initiative (TEI), and Linked Open Data (LOD), accompanied by introduction to professional tools such as Transkribus or Oxygen XML Editor. However, effective TEI teaching typically requires small-scale, project-specific training (Faghihi et al. 2022), an approach that is rarely scalable in regular coursework. This creates a disconnect. While learners gain familiarity with encoding standards, they often lack opportunities to practice real-world workflows. This gap becomes most apparent in the two fundamental tasks of manuscript digitisation workflow: creating structured metadata and transcribing textual content. This highlights the need for a holistic approach in teaching TEI, offering accessible training materials and open-source tools to build user confidence (Terras et al. 2009).

Existing tools like Oxygen XML Editor are powerful but often too complex or inaccessible for beginners. Furthermore, learners rarely encounter real, well-annotated TEI examples or collaborative environments in which to practice and refine their skills. Currently, there is no unified platform that allows learners to explore both metadata creation and transcription in an open, accessible, and pedagogically oriented environment.

Platform Overview

This paper presents MANO - Manuscripts Online, a platform designed to bridge the gap between theory and practice in digital manuscript studies.¹ Targeted at students and researchers in manuscript studies and digital humanities, as well as instructors seeking lightweight, installation-free tools for TEI XML teaching, MANO supports key learning objectives such as understanding TEI structure, creating structured metadata, and experimenting with transcriptions within a single, open-access environment. Operating entirely in the browser and relying on GitHub for data storage,

MANO removes installation and licensing barriers.² It serves as a pedagogical playground where users can engage directly with manuscript description and transcription using user-friendly tools that support the development of core digital humanities skills. The platform is structured around four components (Figure 1).

MANO components and workflow. Instructors upload materials to GitHub (A1); an API (A2) displays them in *Resources* for learners to download (A3). In *Metadata Editor*, users create or upload metadata and download the output (B1); optionally push it to GitHub (B2). An API (B3) loads it in *Metadata Collection*. In *Transcription Viewer*, users upload, edit, and download XML transcriptions (C1).

Resources offers a searchable collection of teaching materials contributed by instructors via the project's GitHub repository.³ Learners can browse contributors and download resources, fostering a growing, community-driven library of teaching content. *Metadata Editor* provides an intuitive web form for entering metadata based on the *TEI Manuscript Description* module.⁴ It guides users through core elements, such as identification, contents, physical description, and history, while linking key fields to Wikidata and OpenLibrary for authoritative, structured data. A live XML preview updates in real time, offering immediate insight into the underlying schema. Completed records can be validated and exported in XML or JSON formats, then contributed to the *Metadata Collection*, an open GitHub repository of user-contributed records.⁵ The interface supports browsing, searching, filtering, and downloading the records in XML, JSON, or PDF. *Transcription Viewer* enables users to upload TEI XML transcriptions and explore them interactively. The interface displays the raw XML code, the rendered text, and digitised manuscript images side by side, with optional in-browser editing and instant preview of updates. For teaching scenarios, MANO provides preloaded sample metadata and transcription files that allow learners to work with real scholarly data in a simplified, hands-on environment.

Conclusion

MANO originated as a teaching tool for introducing the manuscript digitisation workflow of the *Burchards Dekret Digital* project and has evolved into a broader platform for digital manuscript studies.⁶ Rather than replicating the complexity of professional software, it prioritises accessibility and experimentation. Its open infrastructure fosters collaboration and builds learners' confidence in digital methods. By providing intuitive tools for TEI-based metadata creation and transcription, MANO addresses longstanding challenges in TEI pedagogy, including the lack of example-driven, collaborative learning environments (Cummings 2019; Dee 2014). MANO's lightweight serverless architecture, combined with its open-source codebase and transparent data structures, ensures long-term sustainability with minimal maintenance requirements. It aims to grow into a sustainable, community-driven platform for teaching and skill development in digital manuscript studies.

Fußnoten

1. Accessible at: <https://mano-project.github.io/>.
2. The workflows for contributing teaching materials and manuscript metadata are inspired by the collaborative model of HTR-United, a catalogue of training datasets for handwritten text recognition. Accessible at: <https://htr-united.github.io/>.
3. Accessible at: <https://github.com/mano-project/mano-resources>.
4. TEI Manuscript Description Guidelines. Accessible at: <https://tei-c.org/release/doc/tei-p5-doc/en/html/MS.html>.
5. Accessible at: <https://github.com/mano-project/mano-metadata/tree/main>.
6. Accessible at: <https://burchards-dekret-digital.de/>.

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